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THE PHOSPHORYLATION SITE T478 AND SURROUNDING AMINO ACIDS ARE NOT PRESENT IN THE SPIKE PROTEIN OF THE BAT RELATIVE OF SARS-COV-2, YUNNAN_RATG13: COMPARATIVE STRUCTURE MODEL ANALYSIS AND STUDY OF STABILITY AND BINDING TO ACE2 DEBUNKS THE IDEA THAT SARS-COV-2 IS THE RESULT OF LABORATORY MANIPULATION.

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Abstract.

The origin of SARS-COV-2 has generated much controversy and debate. Several so-called experts and pundits have claimed that the Bat relative of SARS-COV-2, Yunnan_RaTG13 has undergone laboratory manipulation to generate SARS-COV-2. Examination of the sequence of the Spike protein (SPp) of Bat Yunnan_RaTG13 shows that the phosphorylation site T478 and surrounding amino acids that are present in SPp of SARS-COV-2 are missing in SPp of Yunnan_RaTG13. Here, through structure model analysis and thermodynamic calculation, it is shown that the binding efficiency of SPp of Yunnan_RaTG13-ACE2 complex is significantly distinct from SPp of SARS-COV-2-ACE2 complex. It is shown that phospho-T478 reduces the stability of SPp of SARS-COV-2-ACE2 complex and the binding efficiency of SPp of SARS-COV-2 to ACE2. Engineering

T478 and surrounding amino acids into SARS-COV-2 would be futile as phosphorylation of T478 resulted in a SPp of SARS-COV-2 that binds ACE2 with lower binding efficiency and a SPp of SARS-COV-2-ACE2 complex that is significantly less stable. The above results clearly debunk the idea that SARS-COV-2 is derived from Bat Yunnan_RaTG13 through laboratory manipulation at the Wuhan Institute of Virology. The suggestion that SARS-COV-2 originated as a result of laboratory experimental manipulation of Bat Yunnan_RaTG13 at the Wuhan Institute of Virology is debunked because prior to the current work, no-one noticed that the phosphorylation site T478 and surrounding amino acids are missing in Bat Yunnan_RaTG13 and the function of phospho-T478 and surrounding amino acids was unknown. One does not engineer a virus that would make it less stable and less efficient at infecting its host cells. The present work shows that phosphorylation of T478 of SPp of SARS-COV-2 by cellular protein kinase such as GSK-3 and Cdk1 will be accompanied by lower and not higher rate of infection. The present work also shows that Pangolin Guangdong MP 789 is most probably an ancestor of SARS-COV-2 and Pangolin is most probably an intermediate carrier of SARS-COV-2 because the phosphorylation sites S477 and T478 and surrounding amino acids that are present within the ACE2 receptor binding domain of the SPp of SARS-COV-2 is also present in Pangolin Guangdong MP 789. It is not clear why research work on Pangolin coronaviruses and Pangolin as intermediate animal carrier of SARS-COV-2 has not received the attention that it deserves.

Introduction.

The origin of SARS-COV-2, the etiologic agent of SARS-COV-2 [1-4] is at the center of much controversy and unscientific, racist and defamatory statement by so-called experts and pundits [5-12]. The clueless Director of the United States' National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases, Anthony Fauci has stated without scientific evidence that "Certainly, the people who investigated it say it likely was the emergence from an animal reservoir that then infected

individuals, but it could have been something else, and we need to find that out. So, you know, that's the reason why I said I'm perfectly in favor of any investigation that looks into the origin of the virus" [13]. Even the President of the United States of America and a number of Senators and Congress Members with zero scientific knowledge of the science of viruses that infect humans or SARS-COV-2 have seen fit to inject their unscientific, racist and defamatory opinions [11]. The self-proclaimed experts and pundits

have stated with zero scientific evidence that SARS-COV-2 is the result of laboratory manipulation of a Bat relative of SARS-COV-2, Bat Yunnan_RaTG13 at the Wuhan Institute of Virology [9-12]. At issue in the arguments of the so-called experts and pundits is the finding that the Spike protein (SPp) of SARS-COV-2 which allows SARS-COV-2 to infect susceptible cells by binding to the ACE2 receptor, contains the "smoking gun" with respect to a furin cleavage site and the codon CGG [9-12,14]. It was argued that the furin cleavage site in SPp of SARS-COV-2 and the codon CGG were too convenient and efficient to have evolved naturally [9-12,14-17]. However, the "smoking gun" has turned out to be a fish story as it has been debunked by Anderson, et al. and Tyshkovskiy, A. and Panchin, A.Y. [14,19,20]. It turns out that the furin cleavage site is present in many coronaviruses and the codon is present in ~3% of the SARS-COV-2 genome [14,21-23].

While the so-called experts and pundits were focusing their attention on the "smoking gun" furin cleavage site and the codon usage of CGG by SARS-COV-2 [7-17], they seem to have either missed or chosen to ignore the fact that within the ACE receptor binding domain of SPp, there is a glaring mismatch

between the SPp of SARS-COV-2 and SPp of Bat Yunnan_RaTG13. Examination of the sequences of SPp of SARS-COV-2 and SPp of Bat Yunnan_RaTG13 shows that the phosphorylation site T478 and surrounding amino acids which are present in SPp of SARS-COV-2 are missing in SPp of Bat Yunnan_RaTG13. It is not clear how the Scientific Researchers at the Wuhan Institute of Virology could have engineered SPp of Bat Yunnan_RaTG13 into SPp of SARS-COV-2 to contain the phosphorylation site T478 and surrounding amino acids when SPp of Pangolin Guangdong MP789 contains the phosphorylation sites S477 and T478, and surrounding sequences (AGSTPCNGVEGFNCYF) that are present in SPp of SARS-COV-2. That Pangolin Guangdong MP789 is a natural ancestor of SARS-COV-2 and Pangolin is an intermediate carrier of SARS-COV-2 are more than likely. Xiao, Y. et al. [24] and Zhang, T. et al. [25] initially proposed that Pangolin coronaviruses could be the ancestors of SARS-COV-2 and that Pangolin could be an intermediate carrier of SARS-COV-2. Wrobel, A.G. et al. [26] showed that SPp of SARS-COV-2 and SPp of Pangolin had identical identical efficiencies to human ACE2. It is not clear why research work on Pangolin coronaviruses and Pangolin as

intermediate animal carrier of SARS-COV-2 has not received the attention that it deserves.

In the present work, through structure model analysis and thermodynamic calculation, it is shown that stability and binding efficiency of SPp of Bat Yunnan_RaTG-ACE2 complex which lacks the phosphorylation site T478 and surrounding sequences found in SPp of SARS-COV-2 are quite distinct from SPp of SARS-COV-2-ACE2 complex and that the phosphorylation sites T95, S477 and T495 within SPp are important determinants of the stability and binding efficiency of SPp of SARS-COV-2 complex. These results debunk the idea that SARS-COV-2 is derived from Bat Yunnan_RaTG13 as the result of laboratory manipulation at Scientific Researchers at the Wuhan Institute of Virology.

Methods.

The structures SPp of SARS-COV-2-ACE2 and SPp of Bat Yunnan_RaTG13-ACE2 complexes were based on the use of structure determinations of SPp of SARS-COV-2 (PDB: 77A94.1) by Zhou et al. [27], SPp of Bat Yunnan_RaTG13 (PDB: 7KJ2.1) by Xiao, T. et al. [28] and the ectodomain of ACE2 (PDB: 6VW1) by Shang, J. et al.[29] respectively. The structures of SPp, Bat

Yunnan_RaTG13 and ACE2 in this study were rendered using SWISS Model pursuant to Waterhouse et al. [30]. Phosphorylation of S477, T478 and T95 of SPp of SARS-COV-2 was performed with FoldX using the Build Model Program pursuant to Guerois, R. et al. and Schymkowitz, J. et al. [31,32]. Docking experiments to identify the SPp of SARS-COV-2-ACE2 and SPp of Yunnan_RaTG13-ACE2 complexes were performed using the ZDOCK program pursuant to Pierce, B.G. et al. [33]. All structures were subsequently rendered, visualized and analyzed by the CCP4 Molecular Graphics Program Version 2.10.11 as described by Mc Nicolas, S. et al [34] and the ZMM Molecular Modeling Program as described by Garden, D.P and Zhorov, B.S. [35]. Determination and calculation of Stability Energy ($\Delta G_{\text{stability energy}}$) and Binding Energy ($\Delta \Delta G_{\text{binding energy}}$) of the protein complexes was performed using the Stability Program of FoldX as described by Guerois, et al. and Schymkowitz, et al. [31,32]. Binding Energy Difference ($\Delta \Delta \Delta G_{\text{binding energy difference}}$) between phospho-protein complexes and dephospho-protein complexes pursuant to Teng, et al. and Nishi, et al. [36-38] from the equation: $\Delta \Delta \Delta G_{\text{binding energy difference}} = \Delta \Delta G_{\text{binding energy}}$ of phospho-protein

complexes - $\Delta\Delta G_{\text{binding energy}}$ of dephospho-protein complexes.

Results.

Examination of the primary structure of the ACE2 Receptor Binding Domain of SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein (SPp) reveals the presence of Serine 477 and Threonine 478 at an important SPp-ACE2 interacting site which are phosphorylation sites for Cdk1 and GSK-3 [38-45]. (Figure 1 and See below). Interestingly, the ACE2 Receptor Binding Domains of SPp of SARS-COV-1 (PDGKPCTPP_ALNCYW) and Bat Yunnan_RaTG13(AGSKPCNGQTGLNCY Y) do not contain phosphorylation site S477

and/or T478 (Figure 1). On the other hand, the ACE2 Receptor Binding Domain of SPp of Pangolin Guangdong MP789 has identical phosphorylation sites Serine 477 and Threonine 478 and surrounding amino acids as SPp of SARS-COV-2 (AGSTPCNGVEGFNCYF). It is not clear how Bat Yunnan_RaTG13 could be manipulated into SPp of SARS-COV-2 when Pangolin Guangdong MP789 has identical phosphorylation sites Serine 477 and Threonine 478 and surrounding amino acids as SPp of SARS-COV-2. Figure 2 shows the structure of SPp of SARS-COV-2-ACE2 complex.

	480	470	477/478	520
Wuhan, China (NC_045512)	NLKP	FERDIS	TEIYQAG <u>ST</u>	PCNGVEGFNCYF
Bat Yunnan_ RaTG13 (QHR63300.2)	NLKP	FERDIS	TEIYQAG <u>S</u> K	PCNGQTGLNCYY
Pangolin Guangdong MP789 (Q1G55945)	NLKP	FERDIS	TEIYQAG <u>ST</u>	PCNGVEGFNCYF
SARS-COV-1 (NC_004718)	KLRP	FERDIS	NVPFSPD <u>G</u>	KPCTPP_ALNCYW

Figure 1. Protein Sequence Alignment of SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein from Wuhan, China (NC 045512), Bay Yunnan RaTG13 (QHR63300.2), Pangolin Guangdong MP789 (Q1G55945) and SARS-COV-1 (NC 004718).

The Stability Energy ($\Delta G_{\text{stability energy}}$) and Binding energy ($\Delta \Delta G_{\text{binding energy}}$) of the SPp of SARS-COV-2-ACE2 complex was estimated to be ~ 781 Kcal/mole and ~ 106 Kcal/mol respectively (Table 1). Phosphorylation of S477 of SPp in the SPp of SARS-COV-2 -ACE2 complex (Figure 3) did not have significant effect on its structure or calculated Stability Energy and Binding Energy (Table 1). However, phosphorylation of T478 of SPp in the SPp of SARS-COV-2-ACE2 complex (Figure 4) resulted in significant decrease in the Stability Energy and Binding Energy of the resulting phospho-T478-SPp of SARS-COV-2-ACE2 complex which were estimated to be ~ 719 Kcal/mol and ~ 49 Kcal/mol respectively. The Binding Energy Difference between dephospho-SPp of SARS-COV-2-ACE2 complex and phospho-T478-SPp of SARS-COV-2-ACE2 complex was calculated to be ~ -57 Kcal/mol.

The calculated Stability Energy and Binding Energy of phospho-T95-SPp of SARS-COV-2-ACE2 complex (Figure 5) was estimated to

be ~ 786 Kcal/mol and ~ 106 Kcal/mol respectively.

Figure 2. Panel A: Ribbon structure of unphosphorylated SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein (SPp) (grey) and ACE2 (orange) complex rendered as described in Method Section. The red spheres represent dephospho-S477 and -T478. Panel B: Realistic rendering of unphosphorylated SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein (SPp) (grey) and ACE2 (orange) complex.

	Stability Energy (ΔG) Kcal/mol	Binding Energy ($\Delta\Delta G$) Kcal/mol	Binding Energy Difference ($\Delta\Delta\Delta G$) Kcal/mol
Dephospho-SARS-COV-2 SPp-ACE2 complex	~781	~106	~ 000
Phospho-serine 477-SARS-COV-2 SPp-ACE2 complex	~781	~106	~ 000
Phospho-threonine 478-SARS-COV-2 SPp-ACE2 complex	~719	~49	~ -57
Phospho-threonine 95-SARS-COV-2 SPp-ACE2 complex	~786	~106	~ 000
Phospho-serine 477/threonine 478/threonine 95-SARS-COV-2 SPp-ACE2 complex	~718	~38	~ -68
Dephospho-Bat Yunnan_RaTG13 SPp-ACE2 complex	~611	~82	~ -24
Phospho-serine 477-Bat Yunnan_RaTG13 SPp-ACE2 complex	~615	~87	~ -19
Phospho-threonine 95-Bat Yunnan_RaTG13 SPp-ACE2 complex	~626	~83	~ -23
Phospho-threonine 95/S477-Bat Yunnan_RaTG13 SPp-ACE2 complex	~628	~87	~ -19

Table 1. Thermodynamic calculations, including Stability ($\Delta G_{\text{stability}}$), Binding Energy ($\Delta\Delta G_{\text{binding energy}}$) and Binding Energy Difference ($\Delta\Delta\Delta G_{\text{binding energy difference}}$) that underlie the binding of dephospho-SPp-ACE2 and various phospho-SPp-ACE2 complexes, and dephospho-SPp-DC-SIGN and various phospho-DC-SIGN complexes.

When SPp of SARS-COV-2 was phosphorylated on T95, S477 and T478, the resulting phospho-T95/S477/T478-SPp of SARS-COV-2-ACE2 complex (Figure 6) had Stability Energy and Binding Energy of

~718 Kcal/mol and ~38 Kcal/mol respectively, and Binding Energy Difference of ~ -68 with respect to dephospho-SPp of SARS-COV-2-ACE2 complex.

Figure 3. Panel A: Ribbon structure of SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein (SPp) phosphorylated on S477 (grey) and ACE2 (orange) complex rendered as described in Method Section. The red spheres represent phospho-S477. Panel B: Realistic rendering of SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein (SPp) phosphorylated on S477 (grey) and ACE2 (orange) complex.

Figure 4. Panel A: Ribbon structure of SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein (SPp) phosphorylated on T478 (grey) and ACE2 (orange) complex rendered as described in Method Section. The red spheres represent phospho-T478. Panel B: Realistic rendering of SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein (SPp) phosphorylated on T478 (grey) and ACE2 (orange) complex.

Figure 5. Panel A: Ribbon structure of SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein (SPp) phosphorylated on T95 (grey) and ACE2 (orange) complex rendered as described in Method Section. The red spheres represent phospho-T95. Panel B: Realistic rendering of SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein (SPp) phosphorylated on T95 (grey) and ACE2 (orange) complex

The above results indicate that phosphorylation of T478 has significant effect on the structure, Stability of the SPp of SARS-COV-2-ACE2 complex and binding efficiency of SPp of SARS-COV-2 to ACE2 and that phosphorylation of T95, S477 and T478 of SARS-COV-2 collectively caused a significant decrease in the stability of SPp of

SARS-COV-2-ACE2 complex and binding efficiency of SPp of SARS-COV-2 to ACE2 in the SPp of SARS-COV-2-ACE2 complex. These results also show that phosphorylation of T95, S477 and T478 of SPp of SARS-COV-2 collectively allowed the host cell to prevent its infection by SARS-COV-2.

Figure 6. Panel A: Ribbon structure of SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein (SPp) phosphorylated on T95/S477/T478 (grey) and ACE2 (orange) complex rendered as described in Method Section. The red spheres represent phospho-T95/S477/T478. Panel B: Realistic rendering of SARS-COV-2 encoded Spike protein (SPp) phosphorylated on T95/S477/T478 (grey) and ACE2 (orange) complex.

Figure 7. Panel A: Ribbon structure of unphosphorylated Bat Yunnan RaTG13 encoded Spike protein (SPp) (grey) and ACE2 (orange) complex rendered as described in Method Section. The red spheres represent dephospho-S477 and -T95. T478 is missing in Bat Yunnan RaTG13 encoded Spike protein (SPp). Panel B: Realistic rendering unphosphorylated Bat Yunnan RaTG13 encoded Spike protein (SPp) (grey) and ACE2 (orange) complex.

Figure 7 shows the binding of dephospho-SPp of Bat Yunnan_RaTG13 to ACE2. The Stability Energy and Binding Energy of dephospho-SPp of Bat Yunnan_RaTG13-ACE2 were calculated to be ~611 Kcal/mol and ~ 82 Kcal/mol respectively, and the Binding Energy Difference with respect to dephospho-SPp of SARS-COV-2-ACE2 complex was ~ -24 Kcal/mol (Table 1).

Figure 8. Panel A: Ribbon structure of phospho-S477-Bat Yunnan RaTG13 encoded Spike protein (SPp) (grey) and ACE2 (orange) complex rendered as described in Method Section. The red spheres represent phospho-S477. Panel B: Realistic rendering of phospho-S477- Bat Yunnan RaTG13 encoded Spike protein (SPp) (grey) and ACE2 (orange) complex.

The Stability Energy and Binding Energy of Phospho-serine 477-Bat Yunnan_RaTG13 SPp-ACE2 complex (Figure 8) were estimated to be ~615 Kcal/mol and ~87 Kcal/mol respectively, and the Binding Energy Difference with respect to dephospho-SPp of SARS-COV-2-ACE2 complex was ~ -19 Kcal/mol (Table 1).

Phospho-threonine T95-Bat
 Yunnan_RaTG13 SPP-ACE2 complex
 (Figure 9) had Stability Energy and Binding
 Energy of ~626 Kcal/mol and ~83 Kcal/mol
 respectively, and the Binding Energy
 Difference with respect to dephospho-SPP of
 SARS-COV-2-ACE2 complex was ~ -23
 Kcal/mol (Table 1).

Phospho-threonine T95/S477-Bat
 Yunnan_RaTG13 SPP-ACE2 complex
 (Figure 10) had Stability Energy and Binding
 Energy of ~628 Kcal/mol and ~87 Kcal/mol
 respectively, and the Binding Energy
 Difference with respect to dephospho-SPP of
 SARS-COV-2-ACE2 complex was ~ -19
 Kcal/mol (Table 1).

Figure 9. Panel A: Ribbon structure of phospho-T478-Bat Yunnan RaTG13 encoded Spike protein (SPP) (grey) and ACE2 (orange) complex rendered as described in Method Section. The red spheres represent phospho-T478. Panel B: Realistic rendering of phospho-T478- Bat Yunnan RaTG13 encoded Spike protein (SPP) (grey) and ACE2 (orange) complex.

Figure 10. Panel A: Ribbon structure of phospho-T95-Bat Yunnan RaTG13 encoded Spike protein (SPP) (grey) and ACE2 (orange) complex rendered as described in Method Section. The red spheres represent phospho-T95. Panel B: Realistic rendering of phospho-T95-Bat Yunnan RaTG13 encoded Spike protein (SPP) (grey) and ACE2 (orange) complex.

These results show that dephospho SPp of Yunnan_RaTG13-ACE2 complex was significantly less stable than dephospho-SPp of SARS-COV-2-ACE2 complex and the binding efficiency between SPp of Yunnan_RaTG13 and ACE2 was significantly lower than the binding efficiency between SPp of SARS-COV-2 and ACE2. Phosphorylation of S477 and T95 caused marginal effect on the Stability of the SPp of Yunnan_RaTG13-ACE2 complex and binding efficiency between SPp of Yunnan_RaTG13 and ACE2.

The above results collectively show that phosphorylation of T95, S477 and T478 reduces the stability of the SPp-ACE2 complex and binding efficiency of SPp and ACE2. Thus, phospho-T95/S477/T478-SPp of SARS-COV-2-ACE2 complex became less stable and the binding efficiency between SPp of SARS-COV-2 and ACE2 became considerably reduced. Engineering SPp of Bat Yunnan_RaTG13 which does not contain phosphorylation site T478 into SPp of SARS-COV-2 which contains phosphorylation site T478 would serve no purpose as it renders SPp-ACE2 complex less stable and the binding efficiency between SPp and ACE2 significantly lower. Engineering T478 into SPp of SARS-COV-2

allows the latter to be phosphorylated by cellular protein kinase such as GSK-3 and Cdk1 which would result in lower and not higher rate of infection. The above results clearly debunk the idea that SARS-COV-2 is derived from Bat Yunnan_RaTG13 through laboratory manipulation at the Wuhan Institute of Virology. One does not engineer a virus that would make it less stable and less efficient at infecting its host cells.

Discussion.

In the present work, it is shown that phosphorylation of SPp of SARS-COV-2 on T95, S477 and T478 resulted in a SPp of SARS-COV-2-ACE2 complex that was less stable with significantly reduced binding efficiency between SPp of SARS-COV-2 and ACE2. The phosphorylation sites S477 and T478 are located at an interacting site of SPp of SARS-COV-2 and ACE2. It is also shown that the ACE receptor binding domain of SPp of Bat Yunnan-RaTG13 lacks phosphorylation site T478 (K478 instead of T478) and surrounding amino acids (AGSKPCNGQTGLNCY^Y) that are present in SPp of SARS-COV-2 while SPp of Pangolin Guangdong MP789 possesses phosphorylation sites T95, S477 and T478 and surrounding amino acids that are present in SPp of SARS-COV-2

(AGSTPCNGVEGFNCYF).

Phosphorylation of T478 was critical in causing significant reduction in the stability of the S_{Pp} of SARS-COV-2-ACE2 complex and the binding efficiency of S_{Pp} of SARS-COV-2 to ACE2. It is suggested that the phosphorylation site T478 arose from its ancestor which is most likely S_{Pp} of Pangolin Guangdong MP 789 and is to the advantage of the host cells as its phosphorylation by cellular Protein kinases including GSK-3 and Cdk1 results in reduced stability of S_{Pp} of SARS-COV-2-ACE2 complex and reduced binding efficiency between S_{Pp} of SARS-COV-2 and ACE2. It is also suggested that phosphorylation of T478 and two other phosphorylation sites, T95 and S477 all of which are phosphorylated by controllers of the cell cycle, GSK-3 and/or Cdk1 [39-45] underlies a cellular response mechanism that serves to prevent or significantly reduce the infection of host cells by SARS-COV-2.

A number of so-called experts and pundits have argued without any scientific evidence that SARS-COV-2 is derived from Bat Yunnan_RaTG13 as a result of laboratory manipulation at the Wuhan Institute of Virology [7-12]. These so-called experts and pundits have made unscientific, derogatory, racist and defamatory remarks and

characterizations [7-12] that are unworthy of Scientific Researchers who work with their brains and hands in the laboratory, A major argument of the so-called experts and pundits which fuels the origin of SARS-COV-2 controversy has to do with the so-called "smoking gun" in respect to the furin cleavage site in S_{Pp} of SARS-COV-2 and the codon, CGG which are alleged to be too convenient and efficient to have evolved naturally [7-12,14-17]. The "smoking gun" is in fact a dud as it has been debunked by Anderson, et al. and Tyshkovskiy, A. and Panchin, A.Y. [14,19,20]. Had the so-called experts and pundits bothered to do some real research work in the laboratory with their brains and hands, and read the scientific literature and instead of opening their mouth without engaging their brains, they would have realized that the furin cleavage site is present in many coronaviruses and the codon CGG is present in ~3% of the SARS-COV-2 genome [14,18].

It is quite unfortunate that a quotation of an elder statesman of the discipline of Virology (David Baltimore) [14-17] has fueled much vitriol that has fanned the unscientific, derogatory, racist and defamatory innuendos and statements of the so-called experts and pundits with no scientific practical

experience of working with viruses that infect humans or SARS-COV-2 [7-12,14-17]. David Baltimore should know better. He should engage his brain before he opens his mouth to the unscientific world. It is true that David Baltimore is quite naive politically. However, he must be cognizant of the fact that unscientific statement constitutes Dishonest Scientific Reporting [46,47] and false rumors can ruin the career of a Scientific Researcher. David Baltimore seems to have forgotten the case of "In the Matter of United States Congress v. Teresa Imanishi-Kari and David Baltimore" [48], when he had to resign from the Presidency of Rockefeller University mostly because of unscientific "proofs" and political vendetta. The Scientific Researcher whom the world has dubbed the "Bat Woman" will most certainly not have a scientific career in the United States after what the unscientific, racist and defamatory so-called experts and pundits [7-12,14-17] have said about her and her research work (See [8] for a discussion of why Segreto, R. and Deigin [9], Cyranoski, D. [10], Sirotkin, K. and Sirotkin, D.[11], Latham, L. and Wilson, A. [12] and Bloom, J.D. et al. [7] are a bunch of unscientific, racist and defamatory individuals. The latest publication of Bloom, J.D. [49] confirms that he is an unscientific, racist and defamatory

individual and not a Scientific Researcher who uses his brain and hand in the laboratory. The unscientific, derogatory, racist and defamatory insinuations of Bloom, J.D. [49] state that "This paucity of sequences could be due in an order that unauthorized Chinese labs destroy all coronavirus samples from early in the outbreak reportedly for 'laboratory biological safety' reasons", "There is no plausible scientific scientific reason for the deletion: the sequences are perfectly concordant with the samples described in Wang et al", "It therefore seems likely the sequences were deleted to obscure their existence. particularly in light of the directive that labs destroy early samples" and "this suggests a less than wholehearted effort to trace early spread of the epidemic". Bloom, J.D. [49] would like the scientific world to think that he has made a major discovery! However, his "smoking gun" is a shameless piece of unscientific, derogatory, racist and defamatory propaganda. One cannot hide something that one has published. All the data that Bloom, J.D. [49] claims to have uncovered are published data [50]. bioRxiv claims to be an independent publisher of preprint articles [51]. In its website, it states that "Articles are not peer-reviewed, edited, or typeset before being posted online. However, all articles undergo a basic

screening process for offensive and/or non-scientific content and for material that might pose a health or biosecurity risk and are checked for plagiarism" which is false because it does conduct a review process that is akin to a Mob Review Censorship Board. It is not clear how and why bioRxiv published Bloom, J.D. preprint article [49] while it acts as a Mob Review Censorship Board for many preprint articles that it deems unsuitable for completely unscientific and arbitrary reasons (The author of this article had two preprint articles rejected by bioRxiv and the reasons were: It is preferable that your article undergoes normal review process with a regular journal or your article does not seem to contain new data. bioRxiv which is supported by Tax Payer's contribution must be transparent in its review process and it must divulge the scientific qualifications of the individuals who review submitted preprint articles to bioRxiv. That bioRxiv acts as a Mob Review Censorship Board is an understatement). Why Bloom, J.D.'s preprint article [49] is published in bioRxiv when it is riddled with unscientific, derogatory, racist and defamatory propaganda, and it also consists of Dishonest Scientific Reporting which is a form of Scientific Misconduct.

It is clear that Bloom, J.D. [49] is an individual who does not work in the laboratory with his brain and hands. Instead of making unscientific, derogatory, racist and defamatory propaganda to malign the Scientific Researchers at the Wuhan Institute of Virology, Bloom, J.D. [7,49] should go back to school to read and study the History and Philosophy of Science, Karl Popper's Logic of Scientific Discovery, Thomas Kuhn's Theory of Scientific Revolutions and Paul Feyerabend's Against Method. In the field of Virology, experiments must be performed in the laboratory to answer a scientific question. In the field of Virology, one does not theorize with doing an experiment with one's brain and hands. One certainly does not make unscientific, derogatory, racist and defamatory conclusions without doing an experiment with one's brain and hands in the laboratory. What is Bloom, J.D. [49] trying to prove except that he is an individual who does not work in the laboratory with his brain and hands and that he is unscientific, derogatory, racist and defamatory? Bloom, J.D. [49] has admitted that his unscientific, derogatory, racist and defamatory conclusions "sheds no light on the origins of the pandemic, nor on why the sequences were removed". Bloom, J.D. [49] and Callaway, E. [52] state that

Wang, M. et al. [50] did not respond to their queries. Why would Wang, M. et al. [50] respond to a bunch of unscientific, derogatory, racist and defamatory individuals.

While the so-called experts and pundits were focusing their attention on the "smoking gun" with respect to the furin cleavage site and the codon usage of CGG by SARS-COV-2 [7-17,49], they seem to have either missed or chosen to ignore the fact that within the ACE2 receptor binding domain of SPp, there is a glaring mismatch between the SPp of SARS-COV-2 and SPp of Bat Yunnan_RaTG13. Examination of the sequences of SPp of SARS-COV-2 and SPp of Bat Yunnan_RaTG13 shows that the phosphorylation site T478 and surrounding amino acids which are present in SPp of SARS-COV-2 are missing in SPp of Bat Yunnan_RaTG13. It is not clear how and why the Scientific Researchers at the Wuhan Institute of Virology would engineer SPp of Bat Yunnan_RaTG13 into SPp of SARS-COV-2. In the present work, it is shown that the phosphorylation site T478 in SPp of

SARS-COV-2 renders it less stable and less efficient to bind to ACE2 whereas SPp of Pangolin Guangdong MP789 contains the exact phosphorylation sites S477 and T478, and surrounding sequences (AGSTPCNGVEGFNCY) that are present in SPp of SARS-COV-2. Pangolin Guangdong MP789 is most likely a natural ancestor of SARS-COV-2 and Pangolin is also most likely an intermediate carrier of SARS-COV-2. Xiao, Y. et al. [24] and Zhang, T. et al. [25] have proposed that Pangolin coronaviruses could be the ancestors of SARS-COV-2 and that Pangolin could be an intermediate carrier of SARS-COV-2. Wrobel, A.G. et al. [26] reported that SPp of SARS-COV-2 and SPp of Pangolin had identical efficiencies in their binding to human ACE2. It is not clear why research work on Pangolin coronaviruses as ancestors of SARS-COV-2 and Pangolin as intermediate animal carriers of SARS-COV-2 has not received the attention that it deserves. It is urged that in addition to Bats, other animals, including Pangolins should be investigated as intermediate carriers of SARS-COV-2.

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